

ETHNOCULTURAL INTEGRATION OF THE MIGRANT MODULE

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Abstract. *In this article, it is noted that immigration increases the diversity of linguistic, ethnic, and confessional affiliations in the countries that receive migrants. This occurs as people involved in cross-border migration typically do not lose their roots in historical traditions or the mental characteristics of their national culture. They maintain their connections to their homeland while, at the same time, creatively assimilating elements of the new culture they encounter.*

As a result, new cultural phenomena arise through the diffusion and hybridization of ethnocultural similarities within and across different cultures. This integration involves the skills of foreign migrants adapting to societal norms, as well as the exchange of national and cultural values. The potential for ethnocultural transformation among migrants contributes to the formation of a universal ethical-humanistic and democratic principle within the acculturation model, which enhances methods and means of integration.

Keywords: *acculturation model, ethno-cultural transformation, disintegrative factor, cascade status, adaptive potential, migrant-phobia phenomenon, migrant module, ethno-cultural tolerance.*

Introduction: Migration processes between countries are creating serious social issues, causing a "cascade effect" for migrants and the countries receiving them. Specifically, the issues are related to the adaptation of migrants coming from various countries and the indigenous population, the formation of the "adaptation effect" to foreign cultures and values, the ability of migrant workers to find appropriate employment in these countries, the opportunities to preserve the results of national-historical civilizations, and the integration of ethnocultural values in the context of ensuring the stable development and security of states. In other words, the flow of "foreign" mass migration actively impacts the transformation of the ethnocultural structure and social relations of these societies.

Achieving this systematically at the state policy level (for example, through official events organized by city or company leaders), and informally (by shaping a positive public opinion about migrants in cooperation with local media) will yield good results. In this case, spreading positive opinions about migration and migrants by politicians and officials can stabilize social relations in society, preventing them from "becoming responsible for all misfortunes."

Considering the multidimensionality of any social phenomenon, it becomes clear that both its positive and negative aspects are directly or indirectly related to the ethnocultural processes arising from migration. The focus is on the formation of the constructive potential of migration in political, cultural, and psychological spheres, the adaptation of migrants to new ethnocultural environments, and the mutual benefits of both parties, which are taken from the "migrant module."

This module was not a reaction to the worsening of the 2015 migration crisis, but rather aimed to form universal humanistic, democratic principles in the attitude of European populations

towards migrants. Later, the decline of the anti-immigration emotional wave, as noted by Eurobarometer, showed the presence of stereotypical behavior patterns related to this module.

The duration of labor migrants' activity and their integration into a new ethnocultural environment shapes the social relationship system between migrants and the indigenous population. The continuity of migrants' generations (their replacement) has a positive impact on the development of the "adaptation potential" of both sides. Sociological studies conducted in 2015 showed that among the total immigrant population, the share of the first generation reached 16%, with this figure exceeding 40% in Switzerland.

As a result of immigration, the composition of the population in the receiving country becomes more diverse in terms of linguistic, ethnic, and religious affiliations. In cross-border migration, people usually do not lose their historical traditions, national cultural traits, or ties to their homeland. At the same time, as they creatively integrate new (in a positive sense) "transmutant" cultural elements, new cultural phenomena arise. In other words, the diffusion and hybridization of ethnocultural similarities take place at the boundaries and crossroads of different cultures.

Thus, a new transnational, ethnocultural phenomenon is formed. The stereotypes in the consciousness of migrants, who understand their affiliation with these social groups, and the changes in their daily behavior and "prism" of social reality, reflect their adaptation to the new environment.

Literature Review on the Topic: Migration processes, ethnocultural integration, migration models, and the sociological, psychological, and ethnosociological aspects of migrants have been studied by several scholars and researchers. Among them, R. Kelly, V. Prashad, Arthur Ahmann, A.V. Lubskiy, I.P. Chernobrov, M.Yu. Apanov analyzed various models of migration and integration, and the interaction of ethnocultural processes as well as social integration issues. Researchers such as Rudolf Lounsborg, Alexander Portes, Richard Scott, and Anthony Giddens have studied globalization and migration processes, focusing on contemporary trends in ethnocultural integration. Central Asian and Uzbek scholars such as K.H. Abdurakhmanov, M.B. Bekmurodov, A.Zh. Kholebekov, M.Kh. Ganieva, Sh.M. Sodoqova, and A.P. Seitov have paid attention to the social, cultural, sociological, and psychological aspects of migration.

Research Methodology: Migration is a natural-social process that continues to evolve, and it cannot be halted. Currently, 3.6% of the global population lives outside their home countries as migrants or immigrants, which highlights the relevance and importance of the topic.

In studying the relationship between migration and ethnocultural integration processes and their socio-economic impacts, comparing migration models in various countries and regions, as well as identifying differences and similarities between integration methods and processes, the structural models of migration are analyzed. These models consider the socio-economic, political, and sociological impacts of migration, and they examine the causes and consequences of migration, especially the integration process in new societies.

Foreign migrants in an unfamiliar, non-traditional ethnic and cultural environment may adopt certain models of assimilation, integration, segregation, or marginalization (or combinations of these). The first two models envision constructive interaction between migrants and the receiving society. That is, migrants either lose their national identity and fully integrate into the society (assimilation), or they integrate while preserving some of their national-mental traits (integration).

According to the British Sociological Centre's report, both migrants (violence against women, theft, etc.) and local populations (burning of migrant shelters, attacks on refugees) show an increase in crimes.

In countries like the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Latvia, where the proportion of migrants is lower than in other EU countries, fewer contacts are established with them. In these countries, survey participants showed that they did not care much about ethnic and cultural relations with migrants. This suggests that the increase in migration flows leads to greater ethnocultural tolerance.

For example, a sociological study conducted in 2014 showed that in Sweden, 90% of respondents, in the Netherlands and Germany, 80%, in the UK, France, and Belgium, about 70%, were willing to work under or establish relationships with migrants.

This study reveals the emergence of the destabilizing factors of cultural diversity in modern societies, where these processes, if left unchecked, could lead to societal fragmentation.

This phenomenon is also reflected in our country in a unique way. For instance, a sociological survey conducted by FJRM in 2019 showed that more than half of the respondents (54.5%) noted that they adapted to the customs and traditions of the regions where they worked. This response was especially common among respondents from Kashkadarya (74%) and Samarkand (67%) regions. On the other hand, 42% of respondents showed that they were unable to adapt.

Thus, the assimilation of the ethnocultural group of migrants is a long, multi-stage, and controversial social, political, and cultural process. The complete assimilation of migrants into the culture of foreign countries is not always possible. Therefore, cultural activities, especially those conducted by Uzbek embassies among migrants, such as regular concerts by Uzbek artists, exhibitions by painters and other artists, and intercultural dialogue, are crucial for successful integration.

The negative consequences of ethnocultural diversity caused by mass migration in receiving countries are related to the inability to resolve conflicts and integrate migrant workers into the new environment. According to Iranian psychologist F. Moghadam, the ultimate goal of the omniculturalism model is to build a society based on the understanding that human nature is universal and dominant, where the development of group differences is preserved.

Of course, these changes, especially the quality of social relations and their nature, are studied by sociologists and anthropologists; the psychological feelings and experiences of migrants by psychologists; the aging or rejuvenation of migrant populations in specific regions by gerontologists and demographers; and their ethnic structure by ethnologists.

To better understand this process, it is necessary to comprehend the concept of "acculturation." Acculturation refers to the process of mutual influence of different social and cultural systems (i.e., exchange of material and spiritual characteristics) between cultures. This concept was initially used to explain cultural changes in Native American tribes under the influence of European colonizers' culture.

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